

The Satisfaction for the Work in the Italian Regions

There was a significant growth in satisfaction with the work done in the southern regions between 2013 and 2019

Istat calculates the value of satisfaction for the work done. Satisfaction for the work done is constituted by the "Average of satisfaction for the following aspects of the work done (scale from 0 to 10): earnings, number of hours worked, work relationships, job stability, distance from home to work, interest in work."

The ranking of satisfaction with work done in 2019. In 2019 Trentino Alto-Adige came in first place for satisfaction with work done with a value of 7.9, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 7, 7. In third place a group of tied regions, namely Lombardy, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Emilia-Romagna, Umbria, Molise with an amount equal to 7.6. Campania and Sicily close the ranking with a value of 7.2 units.

Ranking by satisfaction of the work done by percentage change in the period 2013-2019. If we take into consideration the amount of the percentage change in the period 2013-2019 then in first place we find Calabria with an amount equal to 5.80, followed by Molise with a value equal to 5.56% and by Campania and Sicily in tie with a value of 4.35%. In the middle of the table there are Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna and Umbria with a value of 4.11%. The Trentino-Alto Adige ranking closes with an amount equal to 2.60%, Abruzzo with a value equal to 1.37% and Valle d'Aosta with an amount equal to 1.32%.

North. The value of satisfaction with the work done increased in the North from an amount equal to 7.3 in 2013 to an amount equal to 7.6 in 2019 or a variation of 0.30 equivalent to 4.11%. Specifically, between 2013 and 2014 the value of satisfaction with the work performed remained constant at an amount of 7.3, and then increased in 2015 to a value of 7.4 units, which it retained in 2016 as well. 2016 and 2017 the value of satisfaction for the work done in Northern Italy increased from an amount equal to 7.4 units up to a value of 7.5 units or equal to a value of 0.10 units equal to 1.35 %. Between 2017 and 2018, the value of satisfaction with the work done remained constant at an amount of 7.5 units and then grew further to a value of 7.6.

Center. The value of satisfaction for the work done increased in the Center from an amount equal to 7.2 units in 2013 to a value of 7.5 in 2019 or a variation of 0.30 units equal to an amount of 4.17 %. In the transition between 2013 and 2014 the value of the Center remained equal to a value of 7.2 units. Between 2014 and 2015, the value of satisfaction with the work performed increased from an amount equal to 7.2 units up to a value of 7.3 units or equal to a variation of 0.105 equal to an amount of 1.39% . In 2016 and 2017, the value of satisfaction with the value performed remained constant at an amount of 7.3 units. Between 2017 and 2018, the value of satisfaction for the work performed went to an amount of 7.3 units up to a value of 7.4 units or equal to a value of 0.10 units equal to a value of 1, 37%. Between 2018 and 2019, the value of satisfaction with the work performed went from an amount equal to 7.4 units up to an amount of 7.5 units or equal to a value of 0.10 units equal to a value of 1, 35%.

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South of Italy. The value of satisfaction for the work carried out in the South grew moderately between 2013 and 2019 from an amount equal to 7.00 units up to a value of 7.30 units or equal to a variation of 0.30 units equivalent to a value of 4.29%. Between 2013 and 2014 the value of satisfaction for the work done in the South was equal to an amount of 7 and then increased to 7.1 in 2015-2016. In 2017 and 2018 this value was equal to 7.2 and then grew further to a value of 7.3 in 2019.

Clusterization. Finally, a representation by clusters is presented through the use of the k-Means algorithm with a representation of the t-SNE type. The following clusters are present, namely:

- Cluster 1: Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Sicily, Puglia, Lazio, Abruzzo, Liguria;
- Cluster 2: Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Piedmont, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta, Tuscany, Trentino-Alto Adige, Molise, Sardinia, Marche.

The cluster is created to verify if there are any classifications that can in some way be assimilated to the distinctions between North, South and South. As is evident, with reference to the variable of interest, namely satisfaction with the work done, two clusters are identified, the first of which substantially coincides with the South with the addition of Lazio, Liguria, and Abruzzo, while the second coincides with the Center-North except for Sardinia and Molise.

Conclusions. In summary, what is striking about the satisfaction with the work done is that it is uniform in the Italian macro-regions even though the conditions of work in the North, Center and South are objectively very diversified. A greater divergence in the data would have been expected. Which obviously is not there. The motivation for this alignment may be due to the methodologies used to collect the data or the interview. In fact, the data collected through the interview may not be suitable for detecting substantial variations useful for comparisons between North-Center and South Italy.

Declarations

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